

Exploiting FAIR interoperability from the ELIXIR –UK IUPHAR/BPS Guide to Pharmacology to an expanding range of ligands, targets, publications and patents

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1. Introduction

The IUPHAR/BPS Guide to Pharmacology (GtoPdb; www.guidetopharmacology.org) [1,2], is an open-access, expert-curated, FAIR-compliant (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) online database of pharmacological targets and the substances that act on them. Its reputation for quality is recognised by a Hidden REF award as well as selection as both an ELIXIR-UK and Global Core Biodata Resource. We continue to expand connectivity of our curated entities to external open resources in other quality databases. These consequently offer an expanding range of powerful navigation and data mining options across chemical structures, sequences and document and patent that users may not be aware of but will be outlined here.

2. Methods

GtoPdb regularly submits ligand substances (SIDs) to PubChem every database release at approximately three-month intervals. The majority will be indexed as defined chemical structures (CIDs) and, crucially, selectable mappings to 100s of other useful PubChem chemistry resources but our curated clinical antibodies remain as SID-only protein entries. We have introduced SID-tagging for uniquely specific ligand sets that can be used for further analyses (explained in ref 3). For targets we maintain a UniProt cross-reference set. For journal publications we have enabled the NCBI to provide LinkOuts to all our curated references and also submitted a subset of these that document quantitative interaction data to European PubMed Central (EPMC). For patent numbers included in ligand entries a simple search with “patent” will retrieve these from the GtoP query interface or via matches to curator comments in the SIDs.

3. Results

GtoPdb substances (SIDs): from [Release 2024.3](#) currently numbering 12,874 are selectable from the “Search details” query below

Search results: 1 to 20 of 12874

1. LY310762: GTPL13550: LY-310762...
Source: IUPHAR/BPS Guide to PHARMACOLOGY
Deposit Date: 2024-10-03 Available Date: 2024-10-03 Modify Date: 2024-10-03
SID: 500839970 [CID: 4282258]
Summary PubChem Same Compound

2. Compound 780A: GTPL13559: 3-butyl-8-chloro-1-[3-[5-(4-fluorophenyl)methyl]-2H-tetrazol-2-yl]propyl]-3,7-dihydro-1H-purine-2,6-dione
Source: IUPHAR/BPS Guide to PHARMACOLOGY
Deposit Date: 2024-10-03 Available Date: 2024-10-03 Modify Date: 2024-10-03
SID: 500839969 [CID: 59299562]
Summary PubChem Same Compound

3. Compound 245A: GTPL13558: example 10 [WO2005077950]...
Source: IUPHAR/BPS Guide to PHARMACOLOGY
Deposit Date: 2024-10-03 Available Date: 2024-10-03 Modify Date: 2024-10-03
SID: 500839968 [CID: 59299562]
Summary PubChem Same Compound

Below our SID tags have been used to select 1,995 approved drugs, 393 clinical antibodies and 1,477 from Guide to Immunopharmacology ligands.

GtoPdb Compounds(CIDs): These are generated from curated SIDs by the PubChem rules as defined chemical entities, mostly small molecules but also moderate-size peptides and polynucleotides. These structures are connected by identity, extensive annotations and similarity neighbours within PubChem 119 million. The current 10,679 are below

Search results: 1 to 20 of 10679

1. GTPL13529 (+)-4-enantiomer [PMID: 39046805]: 5-methoxy-2,4-dimethyl-6-[(1S,6S)-4-(4-methylpent-3-en-1-yl)-6-phenylcyclohex-3-ene-1-carbonyl]benzene-1,3-diol
MW: 434.600 g/mol MF: C₂₉H₃₄O₄
IUPAC name: (2S,4R)-1-[(2S)-2-[8-[4-(4-((hexylamino)carbonyl)phenyl)propyl]piperidin-1-yl]-2-hydroxypropan-2-yl]-1,3-thiazol-2-yl]-oxo-lam...
Create Date: 2024-10-03
CID: 172011805
Summary Same Parent Connectivity

2. MW: 419.600 g/mol MF: C₂₀H₂₉N₃O₃S₂
IUPAC name: 2-[amino-[5-(2-hydroxypropan-2-yl)-1,3-thiazol-2-yl]-oxo-lam...
Create Date: 2024-10-03
CID: 172011805
Summary Same Parent Connectivity

3. GTPL13483: YX862: YX-862...
MW: 873.200 g/mol MF: C₄₈H₇₂N₆O₂S
IUPAC name: (2S,4R)-1-[(2S)-2-[8-[4-(4-((hexylamino)carbonyl)phenyl)propyl]piperidin-1-yl]-2-hydroxypropan-2-yl]-1,3-thiazol-2-yl]-oxo-lam...
Create Date: 2024-10-03
CID: 172011804

Users can select useful subsets either from the PubChem defaults (lower right) or custom filters (upper right blue highlights) These include 86% BioAssay results, 83% to patent documents, 23% to PDB entries and 82% vendor links.

3. Results (ctd)

Publications: NCBI LinkOut includes 33,319 PubMed IDs that GtoPdb has added to the SIDs

PubMed search results for 'loproguidpharm[SB]' showing 33,319 results. The graph shows a significant increase in results starting around 2020.

This is an “outer set” that includes contextual references as review articles for ligands and targets. There is an “inner set” of 8,564 papers from which the quantitative interaction parameters have been curated are selectable in European PubMed Central (EPMC) using (LABS_PUBS:"1969")

EPMC search results for 'Discovery of selective Orai channel blockers bearing an indazole or a pyrazole scaffold'. The article is cited by 0 articles and has a PMID of 39232360.

Protein Targets: The GtoPdb chemistry-to-target cross-references in UniProt have increased to 2,290 sequences including Human (1,658), Rat (324) and Mouse (284). These x-refs for other databases enable the visualisation of target overlaps, differences and unique content delineate the druggable genome as shown below.

Patents: Patent number references are added to ligand SIDs that unequivocally map to clinical antibody sequences and exemplified chemical structures. The substance query "IUPHAR/BPS Guide to PHARMACOLOGY"[SourceName] AND patent retrieves 716 SIDs with full patent numbers that can be checked in PubChem for BindingDB SAR extraction [3]

4. Conclusions

This work indicates GtoPdb has made progress to provides users with expanding connectivity out to the wider pharmacology informatics ecosystem. However, navigating between ligands, documents and targets across our own database as well as intersecting with other data sources is challenging. It has thus taken us some time to discover, utilise and track the less-obvious connectivity such as PubChem SID tagging, NCBI LinkOut, EPMC source codes and the UniProt Chemistry cross-references. Notwithstanding, we now have the powerful ability to “slice-dice-and-compare” across these key entities to provide unique insights. We are now exploring further exploitation of this connectivity from GtoPdb. This will include expanding SID-tagging for additional ligand categories and we are also exploring using AI/ML approaches for modelling particular entity sets. Those who would be interested to collaborate on this are welcome to get in touch.

The QR code on the right points to a blog post (reference 5) with extensive details related to this poster including live links to selected results

5. References

1. Harding SD, et al. (2024) *Nucl. Acids Res.* **50** (Issue D1): D1282-1294, PMID: 37897341
2. Harding SD et al. (2024) Oral Communications 4 (this meeting) Tuesday, Dec 10, 15:10
3. Southan C (blog post) <https://cdsouthan.blogspot.com/2022/11/guide-to-pharmacology-selectable.html>
4. Liu T et al. (2024) *Nucl. Acids Res.* Nov 22:gkae1075, PMID: 39574417
5. Southan C (blog post) <https://cdsouthan.blogspot.com/2024/11/exploiting-minable-connectivity-from.html>